

Between Development and Retrogression: The state of Colonial Orissa Canals from inception to independence

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ABSTRACT

Canal irrigation during ancient age had intended for agricultural promotion. Canals were generally constructed by rulers but managed by mostly common peasants. In the matter of irrigation management there was not much intervention of rulers. But during colonial period, the modern management method of canal irrigation was not a pro-peasant one. As per the open official claim, canals were constructed for the protection of crop but in disguise colonial masters had aimed for profit enhancement. To achieve this, they brought various laws time to time starting from 1850 to 1897, which had displeased peasant. On the basis of a few self-created statistics, they tried to show that the Coastal Canal Project of Orissa brought enhanced production and surplus income. But common peasants never had acknowledged the colonial claim rather considered canal as a symbol of colonialism and exploitation. Canal irrigation accelerated the process of commercialization of agriculture, brought water logging problem which caused the problem of malaria, brought the problem of food security by facilitating faster and huge food crop transportation to other provinces and countries with these boosted peasant migration from rural areas to canal colonies which affected rural agriculture because of labour shortage. British management policies and water related laws finally commoditized water which was a big shift from the concept of natural resources to commercial product. This irrigation further broke the economic backbone of the peasants by throwing them out of their hereditary engagement like salt, pottery and weaving industry. Hence, on the one hand canal helped colonizers to maximize income and on the other hand it ruined peasants.

Key Words: Canal irrigation, Bad management, Sufferings of peasantry, commercialization of agriculture, commoditization of water, loss of food security.

Introduction

History of irrigation in the discourse of agricultural history has drawn a great deal of significance in recent years by the effort of some Marxist scholars. In case of Orissa, it retains its high significance, as it was basically a state of agriculture, where ninety percentages of its people were dependent upon agriculture.ⁱ The history of irrigation is as old as agriculture. Human started it with the idea of better irrigation along with better procurement. Initially human started using only natural sources like river, stream and other natural sources along with rain, to which they used to consider God *Varuna* as referred in the Vedic literatures. Whenever there was scanty rainfall, they used to go for different artificial sources like pond and well. Canal construction was also another very important source to carryout irrigation. Those were maintained by the community or by the local heads during ancient period.

The task of construction of canals, wells and ponds remained within the welfare programmes of the local lords or rulers during ancient and medieval period in order to ensure good production.ⁱⁱ The best lively example in Orissa history was the enlargement of Tansuli canal by King Kharavela.ⁱⁱⁱ Again good production used to ensure continuous and unhindered payment of taxes to the rulers. Even special ministers or officials were appointed for the task of the collection of that tax.

But everything changed with the interventions of the British in the agricultural horizon of Orissa. Canal extension was a part of their civilizing project.^{iv} New administrative machinery, which was introduced by the British and was attached with the canal irrigation brought forward a number of changes in the socio-economic and environmental history of Orissa. However, it is in this background, this paper delves into a long trajectory on the state of the canal irrigation of colonial times in general and colonial Orissa in particular.

In colonial India, nothing was done by the British without any ulterior motive. Every project even under the public works department was carried out with profit as a hidden agenda. Canal irrigation was one such project which was executed in Orissa with a pretext of saving agriculture against famine and flood but with an ulterior motive of maximization of profit. However, a Cambridge school historian Ian Stone strongly argued that the canal irrigation in India brought agricultural promotion. Canal proved to be very much useful for protection of agriculture from flood and famine. Both cultivation and production increased.^v Moving one step ahead, Morris D Morris and W H Moreland had argued that the colonial interventions in agriculture improved it considerably.^{vi} What was surprising in their study was that by looking at the demand of food crops and price index, both had perceived that there was a substantial increase in the income of the peasants during the colonial period. But the ground reality was something different as the hiked food crops prices used to not to reach to the poor peasants as there was a big bunch of intermediaries. Similarly, another ground reality was that after paying all kinds of taxes peasants were left with only minimum or nothing.

Oppositely, another domain theory says that there were many problems followed immediate after the extension of canal. Environmental problem particularly the problem of

salinity, health problem and the problem of the loss of fertility capacity of land and the ruination of traditional irrigational sources became very much prominent.^{vii} It also facilitated the process of the commercialization of agriculture. It was used as a medium to colonize colonial agriculture.^{viii}

Coming to the canal historiography of Orissa, many historians have admired and acknowledged the importance of the canals by citing varieties of reasons. Like the Cambridge historians, Ratna Sahoo, supported the theory of the promotion and extension of agriculture.^{ix} Scholars like Braja Bandhu Bhatta and Avaya Kumar Behera argued that both famines and floods were controlled.^x Bhatta^{xi} and Ganeswar Nayak stated because of the enlargement of canals, communication improved. Hence as per his argument canals had helped in developing Orissa's economy.^{xii} Standing with the idea a similar supportive argument was made by Purna Chandra Das. In his argument he tried to show that the merchants of Orissa were highly benefited out of the improved standard of canals.^{xiii} All the above-mentioned points in favour of the benefits of canals have been supported by Gokulananda Patro.^{xiv} Travesty, none of them have studied the canal irrigation from peasants' perspective or taken peasants opinion into consideration while arriving at conclusion.

Canal construction in British Orissa:

The history of modern canal irrigation generally commences from 1855, when a severe flood had broken its economic backbone. This was the first occasion when the colonial government paid little attention to the very problem. But the very event followed no significant government intervention. It followed another disastrous anecdote in 1866, the great famine (*Na-Anka-Durvikshya*) when more or less the entire land ruined. The region had to witness a disastrous setback both from demographic and economic point. The very event followed the formation of a commission, named after its head Sir Campbell as Campbell Commission. The commission had recommended for the construction of few canals in order to meet future challenges like the challenge of 1866. This was the occasion when government invited an Engineer from Madras, Er Arthur Cotton to survey the land and to suggest the possible means to construct canals. During his proposition he cited to the government the manifold economic benefits that they would get out of the construction the canals along with a solution against famines and floods.^{xv}

Hereafter, perceiving economic profit the colonial government started canal construction works from 1869 onwards. Canals like the Kendrapara Canal, the Gobri canal, the Patamundai canal, the Gobri Extension canal, the High-Level Canal, the Taladanda canal, the Machgaon canal, the Coast canal, the Jajpur canal and the Dudhai canal finally came to existence. Up to 1931-32, the construction works were going on and by that time the total length of main canals was 268 miles whereas the total length of the distributary canals was 1302 miles by 1938-39.^{xvi} However, all the canals were utilized in commercial lines till independence to maximize income under the direct authorship of a bureaucracy.

A. Colonial claim of increased production, protection against low rainfall and guarantee for continuous production:

The official claim of the progress of agriculture was noted sincerely by many colonialists in various official records in order to justify the idea of a welfare government in canal colonies. Needless to say, they didn't take peasants opinion into account while accessing the value or importance of various constructed canals. The stalwart claim of the colonial government during the colonial regime was that the Coastal Canal Project was both a productive as well as a protective one. However, colonialists like Colonel Haig, an eminent Engineer; Mr. Wylly, Canal Revenue Superintendent and G. W. Boothby, Secretary to the Govt. of Bengal, PWD boldly argued that there was a substantial increase in the production amount and in the per capita income of the *Odia* peasants. Haig made an observation in 1872 and stated that the average yield of the year on well irrigated land at 25 to 29 maunds of paddy per acre, while that of similar unirrigated land was from 12 ½ to 14 maunds only. In 1878-79 he made 783 experiments and found the increased value of the paddy on irrigated land at Rs. 16-4-9 the equivalent to 15.69 maunds of grain. Mr. Wylly, the Canal Revenue Superintendent had also made a similar kind of opinion by stating a long table in favour of the good impact of canal irrigation on production.^{xvii} The below mentioned table is about his observation.

Figure: 1

Canal Area	Class of land		Irrigated Land		Unirrigated Land	
			Maunds	Seers	Maunds	Seers
High Level canal	First Class	Highest	18	0	17	0
		Lowest	11	24	8	0
	Second Class	Highest	13	8	9	24
		Lowest	12	8	7	28
	Third Class	Highest	8	12	6	25
		Lowest	8	4	5	28
Taladanda canal	First Class		36	0	32	0
	Second Class		38	16	19	8
	Third Class		21	0	11	8
Kendrapara canal	First Class	Highest	25	24	20	22
		Lowest	18	13	11	0
	Second Class	Highest	37	32	24	0
		Lowest	21	21	18	0
	Third Class	Highest	34	32	28	0
		Lowest	13	37	12	24

(Source: Maddox, S. L. *Final Report on the Survey and Settlement of the Province of Orissa, 1890-1900*, Vol.1, Calcutta, 1900, p. 83)

In 1884, the Irrigation Committee had mentioned there was basically a difference of 5 maunds between irrigated and non-irrigated lands.^{xviii}

Like all other colonial officers, G W. Boothby had also boldly claimed even after making all kinds of expenditures the peasants of Orissa could able to earn a very good income from agriculture. He gave a full statistic on that by citing the below mentioned points.^{xix}

Land under canal irrigation:

Yield per acre		Charge per acre	
1200 lbs of rice value			
(Rate of Rs. 2/ per maund) Rs. 24-0-0		Cost of cultivation	Rs. 4-0-0
Value of straw	Rs. 3-8-0	Water rate	Rs. 4-0-0
	-----		-----
	Rs. 27-8-0		Rs. 10-8-0
Income per acre of irrigated land			
	Rs. 27-8-0		
	Rs. 10-8-0 (deduction)		

	Rs. 17-0-0		

Return from non-irrigated land:

Yield per acre		Charge per acre	
522 lbs of rice value			
(Rate of Rs. 2/ per maund) Rs. 9-12-0		Land Tax	Rs. 2-8-0
Value of straw	Rs. 3-8-0	Cost of cultivation	Rs. 4-0-0
	-----		-----
	Rs. 12-0-0		Rs. 6-7-0
Income per acre of unirrigated land			
	Rs. 12-8-0		
	Rs. 6-8-0		

	Rs. 6-0-0		

In 1930-31, the British claimed the average production of paddy was 19 maunds per acre, whereas for non-irrigated land it was 12 maunds.^{xx}

The colonialists were also very much standstill to claim that there was a substantial expansion of cultivation as large tracts of land were brought under the fold of cultivation because of the canal irrigation on the one hand and the attraction of high production and yield. But they did not take the rising demand of food due to the increase of population on the one hand and the force of deindustrialization which made people forceful agriculturalist into their account before judging the thing and passing the conclusion. Interestingly the colonialists have recorded the opinion of peasants who disagreed with the stalwart claim of the colonial government as well as officers and stated that there was nothing any such increase in the production. Maddox had recorded that the peasants had acknowledged the importance of the canal water in the protection against scanty rainfall. Even during late 1930s, it was like an insurance against drought.^{xxi}

B. Colonial Canal: a medium for exploitation and destruction:

Though the canal project of colonial Orissa was a good insurance against drought and flood situations still it was not free from criticism as many negative impacts it brought forward due its bad management by its authorities. Though its bad management profited to the colonial government but it proved to be a great failure in meeting the expectations of peasants. Most of the cases the bad management of it, had violated the natural law, displeased the peasants and became a factor of peasant's antagonism. With this background let us have a look at its manifested problems in a broader manner.

I. Commoditization of canal water:

A significant outcome of the capitalist mode of thinking was the attribution of the institution of private property, and dismantling of community control over various natural resources.^{xxii} Hence, colonialists of the world around had looked for some kind of politics and law to confer the institution of private property by erasing out the status of natural property and declare themselves as the proprietors of the soil by destroying the institution of public property. Hence, capitalism is called a private property economy.^{xxiii} The institution of private property was strengthened by the legislation and implementation various legislations and it further substantiated the capitalist mode of thinking.

During the colonial period, public works served to fix capitalist transformation of nature. Interestingly, Rohan D'Souza argues that varied uses of those public works actually helped slowly to institute capitalist property relations through commodifying nature.^{xxiv} It was a universal phenomenon of all the colonial regions including colonial Orissa. Through public works projects including the railways and canals, it was aimed at controlling the environment and assertions of power. Those projects also served as tools to open out natural resources.^{xxv} David Gilmartin viewed that imperial science helped colonialists to keep control over nature for the maximization of revenue.^{xxvi}

In India the first ever law which paved the way for the exploitation of natural resources in a commercial way was passed in 1865, which had lifted the protection of the forests including the water, land, air forests and other things. As a result of this law, for the first-time peasants were marginalized.^{xxvii} It was an attempt that the institution of private property was attributed. To codify water laws the first ever attempt was made in 1819 under Regulation VI of Bengal Presidency.^{xxviii} But the Bengal Council Act 1867 under its section 2, provision VIII empowered the colonial government to frame certain regulations in order to levy a tax on water. The formulation of various tax codes soon followed. Hereafter it was decided to sell water by volume and by the area irrigated at Rs. 2.50 per acre for 50 acres and above and Rs. 5.00 per acre below 10 acres. In 1869, Act VI laid sales by volume. One rupee was fixed upon per 1000 cubic yards which later on reached to Rs. 6 per acre. In 1872, a new idea of lease came next. Thereafter season wise and crop wise tax fixation provision came. Water tax amount rose from 0.50p. per acre to Rs. 5 per acre gradually.^{xxix} Farmers had no control on the rate of water tax. Selling of water by volume itself suggests that it was completely converted into an economic good from a natural resource. Water started to be considered as a state/private property from a natural resource with the enactment of the Indian Easement Act, 1882.^{xxx}

The Northern India Canal and Drainage Act, 1873 had empowered the government to use and control the water of canals, rivers, natural channels and of all lakes.^{xxxi} The North India Ferries Act of 1878 and the Indian Fishery Act of 1897 dictated canals for navigation purposes.^{xxxii} Hereafter navigation was allowed in various canals for the purpose of levying taxes on users.

Similarly, the Act of 1850 empowered to the British to keep its control over Coastal shipping.^{xxxiii} Prior to 1884, private companies used to decide the amount of fare. But the implementation of the Inland Steam Vessels Act 1884-1890, the British became the sole author of the fixation of fare, which had continued till 1935.^{xxxiv} However, the long path of legislation finally made the colonial government a sole controller of water sources along with canal. This legally permitted to the colonial master to use canal in a commercial way. It paved the way for the commoditization and privatisation of canal water. In a general sense privatisation of water refers to the system of changing lawful public sector responsibility of water to an owner which generally retains the charge as well as power of managing, producing and dispersing water as a profitable good.

Below mentioned table is all about the water revenue collected over many years.

Table: 2

Total Navigational Income (Rs.)		Total Irrigational Income (Rs.)	
Year	Income	Year	Income
1871-72	16510	1871-72	17915
1881-82	39087	1881-82	135254
1890-91	111709	1890-91	249344

1900-01	90485		1900-01	277812
1910-11	NA		1912-13	425617
1920-21	49177		1920-21	518882
1930-31	NA		1930-31	NA
1938-39	67885		1938-39	410054

(Source: Dash, B. G. *History of Canal Irrigation in Coastal Orissa 1866-1947*, Concept Publication, New Delhi, 2020, pp. 123- 136.)

The above table shows that there was an increasing trend of irrigational income up to 1920, but after that it had a downward move. The changes can be attributed to the beginning of national movement and the large-scale involvement of peasants in various Gandhian movements and the observation of no-tax campaign. On the other hand, the rising trend of navigational income started showing a downward journey after 1900-01 as there was the beginning of railway in Orissa. And the majorities of transport and communication were done through railway. But till the eleventh hour of the independence the canal project had economically profited to the colonial masters.

II. Commercialization of agriculture:

The concept of commercialization of agriculture was a colonial development which had helped only to the colonial masters for their mother country's economic development by supplying huge amount of agricultural raw material. In case of Orissa in general and Coastal Orissa in particular, the British paid a very special attention to popularize the cultivation of various commercial or cash crops because it had a very good canal irrigation system. However, it was a thrust project upon the people of Orissa. To popularize various commercial crops, the British had established several Agricultural Research Centres (ARC) as well as agricultural farm which was a deliberate and self-devised policy of them.^{xxxv} Again, in order to motivate the people of Orissa the colonial masters even reduced the canal water rate. The best example of their shrewd policy was seen in Cuttack, where the colonial government reduced water rate from Rs. 2 to Rs. ½ per acre in late 1930s with the basic motive to promote the people of the district to cultivate more jute.^{xxxvi} The agricultural statistics mentioned in various Season and Crop reports of colonial government also marked the fundamental picture that the areas connected by various canals were higher in commercial crops cultivation in comparison to the non-irrigated areas. In case of Coastal areas both Cuttack and Balasore had highest percentages of cash crops cultivation in comparison to Puri district as there were very sound canal irrigation facility.^{xxxvii} So, it would be sufficient to assert that the rise of commercialisation of agriculture used to depend upon canal irrigation to some extent.

III. Loss of Food Security:

Undoubtedly, with the opening of various canals, the medium of communications was improved to some extent. The process became easier and little faster. Water ways which

included both canal way and river way were opted mostly because it was low coast and lesser possibility of theft in comparison to land way prior to the introduction of railway. However, the developed communicational ways brought the problem of food scarcity in several occasions of 19th and 20th century Orissa.

During colonial period, the British traders and merchants were very much impatient that communication mediums were not laid as fast as they wanted. To them an efficient means of transport was a pre-condition for the development of trade and commerce.^{xxxviii} By the end of 1932, there were 285 ½ miles of navigational canals, which were too used for irrigation, 122 miles of branch canals for irrigation only, 1382 miles of distributaries and 26 miles of village canals in Orissa.^{xxxix} However, canals were used as medium to boost the trade and commerce of the British empire. The coast canal used to provide route from Mantai to Hughly. The Kendrapara and Gobri canals used to help in the matter of rice export from Cuttack to Bhadrak and from there to Calcutta. The Taladanda canal connected both the Mahanadi and Kathjuri and by doing so it used to make export easier up to False point and further from there to various foreign countries. The role of High-Level canal cannot be undermined in this regard as it used to provide a direct route between Cuttack and Bhadrak.^{xl}

Water ways (including canals) were used by foreign based navigation companies like the British Indian Steam Navigation Company, the Scindia Steam Navigation Company and the Asiatic Navigation Company. American, British and French Ships used to arrive several coastal regions to export various items.^{xli} Pyarimohan Acharya, a contemporary historian had acknowledged the commercial importance of various canals along with ports as a precursor.^{xlii} They all made use several centres of coastal Orissa as their business hub. Rice was exported in a considerable amount to Madras Port, Cylon, Maldive Island, Calcutta and Mauritius.^{xliii} Exporters used to send out their agents to the villages to purchase crops before they were reaped by making advances to the peasants. It was a common practice throughout the Coastal areas during the colonial regime.^{xliv}

The export trade of the region was basically carried with food crops including rice in substantial manner and non-food crops particularly with cash crops through both water-ways and railway. Canals used to play an important role in this regard prior to the introduction of railway.^{xlv} As a result of that there was no sign of wealth and comfort among the people.^{xlvi} On the one hand the high export of food crops including rice used to create artificial scarcities and substantiating the high intensity of famines and on the other hand it used to leave high pressure on both poor people's purchasing capacity and on their per-capita consumption.^{xlvii} At the time of natural calamities, the prices of food crops used to go up, which used to be very high for poor peasants. As per an estimation in 1865, the normal rate of price was 30-40 seers per rupee. But towards 1867 and 1876 it was around 26 seers per rupee and in 1877 only 21 seers against per rupee. It further reduced to 18 seers between 1886-98.^{xlviii} The hardship of the peasants can best be seen in Cuttack in 1876-77.^{xlix} The unrestricted food export was one of the immediate causes of the scarcities in the late 19th century.¹ The famines and scarcity of 1873-75, 1888-89, 1895-96 are the best examples where man made changes can be seen in a clear manner.

The below mentioned table is all about export value over many years through water ways including canal. Due to the absence of exclusive data related to canal, we are forced to see the combined data of both port and canal.

Table: 3

Total export through water way (Both port & Canal)	
Year	Value of Export in Rs.
1870-71	1336755
1874-75	4391035
1880-81	8148501
1884-85	9653531
1890-91	4235809
1894-95	NA
1900-01	4337101
1904-05	6333985

(Source: Patro, Gokulananda. *History of Communication and Transport in Odisha*, Aayu Publication, New Delhi, 2017, PP. 50-52; Samal, J. K. *Economy of Colonial Orissa 1866-1947*, Munshilal Manoharlal Publication, New Delhi, 2000, pp. 91-93)

Prior to the introduction of railway, the trend of the value of export trade was upward and during post railway introduction period it started showing a downward trend as the lion share of export was made through railway hereafter. But throughout the colonial period canals were used in this regard. Hence it is obvious to presume that canal had played an important supportive role in making the province poor and for the worst sufferings of the people. This made the situation of food crisis inevitable.

IV. Environmental impact:

The canal extension in Orissa also brought one of the most significant environmental problems in Orissa in general and Cuttack district in particular was the extinction of a river named '*Alaka*' when its water diverted into canal. The people or farmers who had settled across the river bank had suffered a lot. They face the problem irrigation. The lamentation of Oriya farmers on the very issue can be seen from two writings from two separate authors like Ramakrushna Nanda and Udayanath Sadngi. Both had titled their songs as '*Alaka*' named after the recently extinct river, which was one of the life-line of the peasants of Jagatsinghpur.^{li} In addition to that the problem of water logging gave birth to various tropical diseases like Malaria, one of the deadly diseases by that time.^{lii} It further had converted thousands of acres of land into arid desert due to increased salinity of the canal area.^{liii} Under the colonial government control there were ten agricultural farms in colonial Orissa and all

those were engaged after research in improving commercial crops. But there was no such scientific measure taken against the problem of salination.^{liv} Like in all other cases once again the canal system put a big question on the environmental sustainability and proved very much cursed for the progress of Orissa.

V. Bad impact on Rural agriculture and Demographic pattern:

One of the major changes during the colonial regime was that there was a large migration of people to various nearby irrigated areas. It was not a sudden outburst. Throughout nineteenth century there were around twenty times famines and scarcities.^{lv} The long years of bad experience due to different natural calamities (particularly famine and scarcities) created an apprehension among them, which forced them to migrate other areas which were having a good irrigation facility.^{lvi}

Below mentioned statistics can help us to have a glitch on the issue.

Table: 4

Increase of density of population in irrigated area of colonial Cuttack District					
Thana	% of land under irrigation	Density of population			
		1881	1891	1901	1911
Jagatsinghpur	21%	685	725	764	770
Tirtol	9%	438	423	461	470
Salepur	31%	874	893	899	963
Kendrapara	19%	650	714	771	832

(Source: O'Malley, L.S.S. *Census of India, 1911*, Vol. V, Part III, Calcutta, 1913, P. 75)

As a consequence of the migration, there was acute shortage of labour in various coastal districts. It had directly impacted upon agricultural operations and construction of public works. It was a situation when labourers from Bengal in general, Midnapore in particular entered into Orissa to be engaged after various construction works.^{lvii} The magnitude of the actual economic loss during the period may not be high but the process must have substantiated the economic deterioration.

VI. Supportive pillar for the colonization of indigenous market and de-industrialization:

As said earlier canals were enlarged both for both navigation and irrigation purpose. Economically both the facility had procured a very good revenue for the colonial master. With the opening of canals non-Oriya merchants found their way to Orissa in large numbers whose primary motive was to maximize profit out of trade and commerce. Outsiders like rice merchants basically Mohammedans from Bombay along with Koomutees from Madras, Marwary cloth merchants from Jaypore and Marwar and skin traders from Afganistan had dominated the markets of Orissa.^{lviii} Further in the colonization process English traders'

agencies like Messrs. Brett Brothers, Messrs. Chambers and Co. and Messrs. Valetta and Co. had dominated several areas of Cuttack, Puri and Balasore. There was very little scope for the Odia merchants in the trade and commerce arena as they were economically poor.^{lix}

With the influx of outsiders, markets of Orissa were heavily flooded with machine made foreign goods, which were superior in quality and cheaper in rate. Similarly, Liver pool salt started dominating Orissa's salt market too. Imported goods included salt, spices, cotton goods, and kerosene oil. As a result of that, the indigenous handicraft industry, salt industry along with other artisanal skills had to face a disastrous challenge and finally, had received a disastrous setback. Many of the skilled persons had shifted their profession to agriculture and became agricultural labourers. Out of different local industries, the most suffered were the handicraft industry and slat industry.^{lx} Throughout 19th century, import trade was confined to only finished goods.^{lxi} At the beginning of 20th century cotton goods were the chief import of Orissa,^{lxii} which had been a trend since late nineteenth century.^{lxiii} Prof. Atul Ch. Pradhan had maintained his own stand on the basis of the narration by Fakir Mohan Senapati that even till the late nineteenth century the weaving skill was alive because of the absence of the communication facilities to various regions. By the end of nineteenth century, cotton weaving and spinning became an extinct profession. It must have been because of the development of canal navigational ways. As per the census report of 1901, around 33,000 weavers were there in Cuttack and out of them many weavers had left the profession as their local weaved garment didn't have demand in front of the machine made chief and designed and refined cotton items. Similarly, out of 56,000 weavers, around only 9000 were still engaged in the hereditary livelihood where as others were not in touch.^{lxiv} It was only because the development of communication mediums. The precarious condition of the local skilled persons was so much so that, the Gem of Orissa, Pandit Gopabandhu Das, once raised his voice in the Bihar and Orissa Legislative Council and stated:

“It is needless to say that weaving has from time immemorial been the cheap cottage industry in this country but most of the handloom weavers have under the peculiar economic pressure caused by foreign influences, been driven out of their family occupation.... A movement organised for the revival of the industry will not only help a dying community but will foster a spirit for new industry among our artisanal classes”^{lxv}

Similarly, in case of salt industry, it was seen that during colonial region Liverpool salt used to pour into Orissa in substantial amount and replaced local salt industries. Hence the industry was transferred to foreign hands.^{lxvi} By looking at the 40,000-indigent people of Balasore, Cuttack and Puri districts, who were deprived of their livelihood and lost their salt industry due to the heavy demand on England salt Gopabandhu Das made his observation in his own words:

“When I see the great body of labourers suffering year by year for want of employment.... I can't but be wail the loss of Orissa has sustained at the hands of officers....”^{lxvii}

As we don't have separate data for canal transport, we are forced to see the united statistics of both ports and canals for better understanding.

Table: 5

Total import through water way (both Canal & Port)	
Year	Value of Import in Rs.
1870-71	1356087
1874-75	3592587
1880-81	5646953
1884-85	9115021
1890-91	3972039
1894-95	NA
1900-01	4161364
1904-05	2770767

(Source: Patro, Gokulananda. *History of Communication and Transport in Odisha*, Aayu Publication, New Delhi, 2017, pp. 50-51; Samal, J. K. *Economy of Colonial Orissa 1866-1947*, Munshilal Manoharlal Publication, New Delhi, 2000, pp. 91-93)

As said earlier, after the introduction of railway, the export and import transactions were mostly done through railway, that was the reason why after 1900, there was a declining trend. However, the trend shows that there was higher influx of European goods in Orissa markets. Though, due to the absence of proper statistics on the influx of the Europeans along with the amount of European products entered into Orissa, it is very much difficult to access the proper role of canal transport in this regard but it can safely be assumed undoubtedly along with other means of communication systems, Canal navigation brought fatal to the indigenous market system as well as indigenous industries and substantiated the process of the colonization of market system as a supportive pillar.

VII. Unsubstantiality of peasants

With the enlargement of various canals, several manifested problems followed one after another. As a direct consequence of that instability of peasantry became inevitable. The foremost one was that it snatched away the self-sustaining nature of the Odia peasantry, as they had the practice of using various traditional sources of irrigation like tank, well, pond, river or natural water streams etc. Old or traditional sources of irrigation were not promoted or maintained as those were not remunerative for the British government. The power of the fixation of water tax rate, date and amount to release water and distribution of water were completely in the hands of the newly established bureaucracy, where peasants had no say, which was a complete opposite one to the older practice of community management of water

sources, where they had self-control or sometimes very lesser control on behalf of the royal authorities on the management of irrigation affair.^{lxviii}

The monopolization of water tax rate fixation was very much because of which peasants used to suffer like anything. Under the system they were required to pay the amount, whether they used water or not. Earlier it was tax-free or very nominal.^{lxix} Initially Rs. 1 was fixed per acre irrigated land which increased up to Rs. 6 per acre during the colonial regime.^{lxx} By that time it was very much difficult for the peasants to pay the amount as there was no substantial increase in their income because of irrigation. However, as stated above it had guaranteed a very good amount of income to the colonial government.

Further, needless to say that peasants were thrown out of their hereditary lively-hood with the massive import of the European goods. The provision of long-term lease in order to irrigate agricultural land was a matter of peasant's instability. There was nothing like sincerity in the matter of the discharge of canal water, even quantity was not adequate.^{lxxi} So for the large-scale increase of impoverishment canal played a supportive role along with other British policies. During the national movement, canal was perceived as a symbol of colonialism and exploitation by the poor peasants. The best example of their severe antagonism against canal was different attacking and burning issues in various regions of Orissa during the national movement. On 26 August of 1942 in *Jajapur* there was a severe attack on the irrigation rest house by the peasants. There were around 10 different cases of the burning of canal revenue offices along with PWD offices in the same division. Similarly on 31st August 1942, in *Jagatsinghpur* division there was a burning issue of canal revenue office.^{lxxii}

Conclusion:

To conclude, the canal irrigation introduced by the colonial government on the pretext to save agriculture, as per the official report had helped them to keep a positive picture of a welfare government in front of the uneducated peasants for a temporary period until it was considered as symbol of colonialism. It was perceived by the colonialists as a supportive pillar for the promotion of agriculture whereas it was considered not more than of an insurance against drought. The actual problem was not with the canal irrigation but with its bad management, monopolized and commercial usage which had helped mostly only to the colonialists.

From a peasant perspective, in comparison to its positive impacts, its negative impacts were more. The high taxation policy including water tax was one of the direct issues which had antagonized peasants and made them to perceive it as an extra financial burden and a symbol of colonial subjugation. Colonial laws further changed the natural resource into a commercial good. Water logging problem and the problem of salinity was very much painful for the peasants. Its bad management made Malaria a big public health concern. The enlargement of canals further facilitated faster and huge transport of food crops from Orissa to other provinces and countries which brought the question of food security. In a similar way canals doubled peasants' sufferings by outing them from their long driven hereditary

engagement. This had happened when vast number of metallic utensils, British manufactured cloths and salt found different nook and corner of Orissa through different canals. Canal colonies further attracted rural peasants to migrate and settle in canal colonies as canals used to stand as a security element against complete or partial failure during low rain or drought. As a result, the shortage of labor in rural areas to perform agricultural works became a matter of much concern. Commercialization of agriculture became again a new phenomenon in canal colonies. Hence it is obvious to claim that the usage of canals in a commercial line was the root of all negative changes. That is the reason why during the national movement of Orissa, canals were seen as symbols of colonialism and exploitation. Canal revenue houses were burnt and attacked. To conclude the project was not a pro-people project because of its wrong management policies.

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